

WAYS TO INCREASE THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS BY SHAPING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation This article explores effective strategies to increase student social engagement by shaping educational activities within the school system. The authors emphasize the significance of fostering positive, stable motivation among students as part of the educational process, which not only enhances individual academic performance but also supports the broader socio-educational goals set by national initiatives. This motivation is linked to socialization practices and group activities, allowing students to engage in meaningful educational experiences that promote self-awareness, autonomy, and the development of key social competencies.

Key concepts discussed include positive stable motivation, educational process organization, the competency-based approach, and the importance of subjective teacher-student interactions in nurturing student autonomy and motivation. The article suggests implementing a model focused on practical, active learning techniques, group activities, and teacher-student interaction to foster sustained educational motivation. The research highlights the influence of both internal and external factors on motivation, including the learning environment, individual self-esteem, and academic goals.

Keywords: social activity, educational motivation, positive stable motivation, teacher-student interaction, socialization in education

School education today represents the longest stage of human education and is one of the decisive factors both for individual success and for the long-term development of the whole country. The formation of positive motivation of students for educational activities is one of the main tasks of the educational system and is reflected in the target program for the development of the public education system until 2030.

Today, within the framework of the project of the national educational initiative "Modern School" in our country, the following have been developed and approved for general educational institutions that will be realized on their

model projects, taking into account Advanced International experience: special education standards and programs of teaching; special requirements for the organization of the educational process; list of adapted teaching literature; the procedure for assessing general educational institutions in order to determine the appropriate level;

The change in priorities in the national educational system, the search for the conditions for the interaction of subjects and subjects of the participants in the pedagogical process put the most important task of developing a positive stable motivation of students. With the growing interest in the subjective component of the educational process based on a new educational strategy based on a competency approach, the attitude towards the result of education and the process of determining the personal fate of the student has changed.

Pedagogical aspects of social motivation in the development of the worldview and culture of students R.Safarova, D.Temirov, S.Babajanova, Sh.S.Sharipov, B.Ziyomukhammadov, M.Ochilov, N.Muslimov, didactic possibilities of educational motivation in the development of social activity and creativity in students o.Musurmonova, E.Goziev, B.Adizov, S.Davletshin, U.Solomov, M.Abdullaeva was studied in the scientific research of leading scientists of our country, such as. I. from scientists of the countries of the Commonwealth of independent states.Plodlacijs, A.T.Svetkova, G.A.Bokareva, V.S.Iliga, Z.P.Shabalina, G.I. Tshukina's research work covered socio-psychological issues of communicative competence and communication. Analysis of philosophical and psychological and pedagogical literature, study of the experience of schools revealed the following contradictions:

many manifestations of a spontaneous motive for the educational activities of students in the middle of a social phenomenon for the manifestation of a positive stable motivation for the educational activities of students and the orientation of the participants of the pedagogical process of the modern local school educational process towards the subject-subject relationship; The demand for students with positive stable motivation and the absence of programs for the formation of positive stable motivation;

The orientation of teachers to the person-oriented and systematic activities of teaching schoolchildren in the educational process and the absence of a model in the real conditions of school pedagogical practice.

Theoretical studies and school experience developed to date show that motivation is a variety of motives, motives, needs, interests, aspirations, goals, aspirations, motivational attitudes or inclinations, ideals, etc. the broad meaning

implies the determination of behavior in general. The study and generalization of conclusions about the essence of positive stable motivation, which is present in psychological and pedagogical research, made it possible to formulate the basic definition used in the research process.

Positive stable motivation is a set of motives that determine the active, personal bias attitude of the student to study, ensuring the relative duration of effective actions aimed at regulating the satisfaction of his needs and interests, mastering generalized methods of solving it.

An analysis of the essences and key factors that determine the manifestation of positive stable motivation in the middle classes allows us to confirm the following:

educational motivation is characterized by a complex structure as a kind of motivation, one of the forms of which is the structure of internal and external motivation; important features of positive motivation, such as stability, degree of intellectual development and connection with the nature of educational activities;

The main factors that prevent the manifestation of positive motivation are: failure to achieve success, personal anxiety, low self-esteem, external attribution;

The main determinants of the educational activity of an individual are the motivation of achievement and certain characteristics of the individual, first of all, autonomy; positive stable motivation is determined by several factors inherent in this activity. Firstly, it is interconnected with the structure of the educational system and the type of educational institution, in this case a school where educational activities are carried out; secondly, the organization of the educational process; thirdly, the subjective characteristics of the student (age, intellectual development, abilities, degree of aspiration, self-esteem, his interaction with other students, etc.); fourth, the subjective characteristics of the teacher's interaction with schoolchildren and, first of all, his system of relations with the student;

Positive stable motivation, like any other type, is characterized by the dynamics of orientation, stability and manifestation in educational activities.

Taking into account the above rules allows the pedagogical community of the school to form an important and complex task - a positive stable motivation for educational activities of high school students in the educational process.

The educational process of the school affects the formation of positive motivation by organizing group forms of students, which contributes to the

socialization of their personality, which does not sufficiently affect children of families and households, directing them to the formation of motivation for success, including educational activities.

This fact assumes the development and implementation of a model for the formation of a positive stable motivation for educational activities of schoolchildren.

The developed model for the formation of a positive stable motivation for educational activities in the process of teaching at school is based on the following principles: scientific and systematic, subjective; consciousness, activity and independence; development and activity, practical orientation; collectivism; reflection.

The mechanism for the formation of a positive stable motivation of educational activity in the educational process of the school consists of the main stages: goal setting, determining the structure of the educational movement, Operation-cognitive, basic selection of organizational forms of work, activity-operational, reflection, assessment of adolescent activity.

We looked at the group activity of students as a sum of cases of pedagogical support for the activities of students, in which not only a positive stable motivation of students to study is formed, but it manifests itself. On personal achievements, the formation of a positive motivation motivation for educational activities is determined. For all three components of positive stable motivation for educational activities, differences in the manifestation of positive stable motivation of students for educational activities were identified in the experimental and control groups of schools;

When comparing test results in control and experimental groups of students, it should be noted that there are significant differences between them in the lower and middle level manifestation of internal motivation. The management team typically has a lower level and less moderate level for the types of activities offered to students during the learning process.

Positive stable motivation for educational activities is determined by a number of specific factors for this activity: the educational system itself, in this case the school Institution; Organization of the educational process; subjective characteristics of the student (age, intellectual development, ability, degree of aspiration, self-esteem, its interaction with other students, etc.); subjective characteristics of the teacher's interaction with schoolchildren.

The formation of positive stable personal motivation is a complex and long - term process of active interaction between a teacher and students in certain

conditions that helps to transfer the external motivation of students to an internal state: to involve students in real practical activities. group activities; the use of active teaching methods that contribute to the development of interests for positive emotional experiences in the lesson; an increase in the need of students to work on themselves. It turns out that as a result of the implementation of the model for the formation of a positive stable motivation for educational activities in the educational process at school, high school students have formed positive stable motivation for educational activities due to need: intellectual self-awareness in the classroom, skills and qualifications of educational activities in the group, readiness to self-assess abilities.

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